

A STUDENT TO STUDENT MENTOR MECHANISM IN AN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER ENVIRONMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10334986>

Abstract. *Students will find it difficult to get used to different forms of teaching such as special subjects and lectures, seminars, practical training, laboratory, training and industrial practices. Unlike school, institutions of higher education do not cover the entire study period, but one or several semesters. The constant change of teachers creates difficulties even for a first-year student.*

The article highlights the issues of introducing a student-to-student mentoring mechanism that allows helping unsuccessful students and supporting them during the adjustment period in the environment of the educational cluster.

Keywords: *educational cluster, educational system, material, lesson, seminar, laboratory, practical training, adaptation.*

The economic, social and cultural needs of society characterize the state of the educational system, and also affect the composition and content of education of HE graduates. Creating innovative educational clusters as the most advanced forms of integration of the real sector of education, science and economy in order to concentrate the intellectual and technological potential of large industrial companies, research institutes and educational institutions is one of the urgent tasks today.

The core of the educational cluster is usually formed by strong enterprises and companies, at the same time, it should be noted that competitive relations are maintained in cooperation between them. In addition, in the context of such clusters, new knowledge and technologies are disseminated and introduced, which leads to the development and production of complex, complex innovative products and competitive advantage [3].

Also, educational clusters have a synergistic effect, as a result of which the interconnected cluster members: an integral complex of various companies, enterprises and organizations provide the regional economy more than the sum of its individual representatives. Therefore, the main factor of the success of the cluster is the relationship between all its participants and maintaining the economic independence of each one [4].

According to G. U. Matushansky and others, the union of various companies, enterprises, suppliers of specialized services, resources and infrastructure, scientific and educational organizations, which are connected by territorial proximity, complement each other and separate enterprises, increase the competitive advantages of companies, forms a cluster. The cooperation of all its members is carried out continuously through the exchange of personnel, technologies, innovations, sharing of resources, services, infrastructure development and marketing [4].

In the educational cluster environment, the student-to-student mentor mechanism involves interaction between students of the same educational organization, where one of the students has a high level of knowledge, and he has organizational and leadership qualities that allow him to

significantly influence the learner. The tradition of "Master-disciple" is of great importance in scientific research and innovative activities. These relations were analyzed by E. Yusupov [7], S. Shermuhammedov [6], O. Sharafiddinov [5] and other scientists.

The purpose of this mechanism is to provide comprehensive support to students with special educational/social needs or temporary assistance in adapting to new educational conditions (including adaptation of disabled children). The student-mentor mechanism is to help students realize their leadership potential, develop skills and meta-competences, help them adapt to new environmental conditions, create favorable conditions and environmentally friendly relations in the educational organization, and form a stable cluster community and a community of grateful graduates.

As a result of the correct organization of the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster environment, they are highly involved in all social, cultural and educational processes of the educational cluster organizations, which undoubtedly positively affects the emotional atmosphere in the team, the loyalty of the organization, students and future graduates to the organizations in the cluster field, and the general state of the rest of the community. has an effect.

Resolution No. 226 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2008 "On awarding and financial incentives for talented young people of Uzbekistan" and Resolution No. 781 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education dated August 29, 2019 "Directed to strengthen the selection of representatives of science among students of higher educational institutions" In order to ensure the implementation of the order "On Targeted Measures", it is to ensure that every student has mastered professional processes perfectly, has skills at the level he can perform, can think creatively, has morals, is morally mature, and is intellectual. In this, professional skills, professional culture, professional ethics and professional education are formed for the student according to the specialization.

In this environment, learners will have the necessary motivation for cultural, intellectual, physical development, self-awareness, as well as the development of necessary competencies. As a result of introducing the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster environment:

- increase educational efficiency, improve the psycho-emotional state in the educational institution;
- increase in the number of visitors to creative circles, associations and sports sections;
- quantitative and qualitative growth of successfully implemented educational and cultural projects;
- reduction of the number of adolescents registered in internal affairs bodies and psychoneurological dispensaries;
- issues of reducing the number of complaints of parents and teachers related to conflicts between organizations of social vulnerability, education cluster can be highlighted.

Implementation of a student-to-student mentoring mechanism in a tutoring cluster environment may vary depending on the needs of the mentor and the resources of the mentor as a result of changing roles. Taking into account the experience of educational organizations, the main options for the student-to-student mentor mechanism can be:

- "successful - unsuccessful" interaction, a classic option of support to achieve good educational results;

- "passive-leader" interaction, team adaptation or psycho-emotional support with development of communication, creative, leadership skills;
- peer interaction, during which skills are exchanged, for example, when a teacher is a critical thinker and a mentor is a creative thinker;
- mutual support, joint work on the project.

In an educational cluster environment, the student-to-student mentoring mechanism can also be implemented in extracurricular activities. It is important to join "class hours", organize joint competitions and project work, attend sports/cultural events together (especially for adaptation tasks) to help develop a sense of belonging.

In the educational cluster environment, the student-to-student mentoring mechanism can be used in activities such as design activities in schools, classroom hours, extracurricular activities, preparation for school community events, volunteering.

At the moment, with the pursuit of fundamental changes in the educational and socio-cultural sphere, the need to introduce a student-to-student mentoring mechanism is of great importance in changing thinking, setting goals and actions, as well as solving issues related to economic problems. The importance of a harmonious and systematic transformation of these areas sets two main goals for all educational cluster organizations:

- 1) Ensuring competitiveness of graduates;
- 2) education of a mature and socially responsible person.

General cultural, general professional goals cannot be achieved without creating a system for supporting and developing the spiritual and moral values and cultural traditions of the country's population. Such a system should facilitate self-determination and career direction of all students. The most effective strategy to meet the above goals and objectives is the use of mentoring methodology, within the framework of which it is possible to comprehensively support students of different levels and forms of education.

Mentoring is a universal technology for developing experience, knowledge, skills, competencies, meta-competencies and values through informal mutually enriching communication based on trust and partnership. In accordance with the laws of development of a new type of culture, the knowledge, beliefs, views, and initiatives coming from adults are not fully understood and implemented by young people. The psychological characteristics of the new generation are such that the most effective perception of experience occurs in interaction and cooperation with peers. We can add that during the student period, the influence of the social institution of the family weakens to a certain extent, the emphasis shifts to peers, communication with them becomes an important source of experience, a means of socialization. This challenge defined a student-to-student mentoring mechanism in an educational cluster environment. The project is aimed at creating an effective system capable of maximizing the full potential of the mentor-student and the mentored student, necessary for successful personal and professional self-realization in the modern uncertainty.

The following main tasks are performed when introducing the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster environment:

1. Development and step-by-step implementation of the student-to-student mentor mechanism model;
2. Conducting a series of educational and educational events for the student-to-student mentoring mechanism;

3. Involvement of the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in various levels of activities, various forms of mentoring activities;

4. Development and presentation of partnership products.

The structural and meaningful model of the formation of the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster envisages the following:

1. Diagnostic component;
2. Target component;
3. Value-semantic component;
4. Content component;
5. Technological component;
6. Resource component;
7. Effective component;
8. Assessment and diagnostic component.

In the environment of the educational cluster, the following forms of activity are used when applying the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in extracurricular activities:

- Design, research and creative activity;
- Joint participation or organization of events;
- joint participation in events such as Olympiads, competitions, championships of professional skills;
- Sports and cultural events;
- Volunteering;
- Excursions to institutions within the educational cluster;
- Vocational tests, vocational training within the framework of early career guidance;
- Skill classes;
- Coaching;
- Training.

Among the problems associated with the implementation of the student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster environment, one can single out the lack of time for mentors and coaches. This problem can be solved through weekend meetings and online communication. Cooperation with coaches is organized according to the plan and includes such forms of mutual cooperation as consultations, master classes, trainings, conversations.

When introducing a student-to-student mentor mechanism in an educational cluster environment, relationships are built on a friendly basis, as a result of which students freely share their experiences and concerns with their mentors. When introducing a student-to-student mentoring mechanism in the educational cluster environment, students learned to plan their steps to achieve a goal, pay attention to organizing preparation time, and find the necessary resources. They gained confidence in their abilities, learned to manage their emotions before public speaking, and confidently expressed their point of view.

In the educational cluster environment, the student-to-student mentor mechanism in the form of interactive communication technologies, as coaches, try to attract students' attention to learning the content of the educational material, try to form their own opinions, critical and logical thinking, as well as develop general and professional skills. They will acquire the necessary competencies to further develop these experiences in their future professional activities.

This mentor allows students to confidently demonstrate their skills during practical training, professional skills competitions, and take the first steps on the career path. Along with experienced, "wise" experts, students themselves prove their competence by passing tests in conditions close to real conditions.

They will be able to inspire others and will be ready to provide expert, consultant and psychologically serious coaching support not only to the opponents of the next championship, but also in preparing for the exam.

The introduction of a student-to-student mentor mechanism in an educational cluster environment allows solving a number of problems, such as helping unsuccessful students and supporting them during the adjustment period.

First-year students find it difficult to adapt to a new educational system, many of them begin to live independently for the first time. They do not know how to work with literature, record material, which leads to low-quality independent preparation for classes, seminars, laboratory work and practical training in various fields. Many students get into a stressful situation during the session.

It will be difficult for students to get used to special subjects and different types of classes: lectures, seminars, practical training, laboratory, educational and production practices. Unlike school, institutions of higher education do not cover the entire study period, but one or several semesters. The constant change of teachers creates difficulties even for a first-year student.

It is important that the student easily adapts to groups and finds his "place" in the group. The faster a student can adapt and occupy a certain position, the easier it will be for him to study. Every student has to get used to the educational system, new students and teachers, new living conditions and new social role. A student cannot solve many problems alone. In this regard, the introduction of the student-to-student mentor mechanism to students in the environment of the educational cluster will lead to a positive solution to the problems in this regard. Their activities are focused on helping 1st-year students to successfully adapt to student life, ensuring the unity of teaching and educating students, strengthening the influence of the pedagogical team on the formation of the future professional personality.

Conclusion

In the educational cluster environment, the student-to-student mentor mechanism can become an effective environment for forming a new educational strategy aimed at forming the skills, practical experience and metacompetencies necessary for the quality implementation of personnel policy; involving students in various forms of mentoring; personal and professional growth of students; increase the quality of professional training of specialists; has a positive effect on the professional and personal development of the teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг қарори. Ўзбекистон иқтидорли ёшларини тақдирлаш ва моддий рағбатлантириш тўғрисида. 2008 йил 13 октябрь. 226-сон.
2. Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлигининг буйруғи. Олий таълим муассасалари талабалари орасида илм-фан вакиллари селекциясини кучайтиришга йўналтирилган мақсадли чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида. 2019 йил 29 август. 781-сон.

3. Захарченко, Е.С. Формирование кластера вторичных ресурсов как института инновационного развития на мезоуровне: автореф. дис. ... канд.экон.наук: 08.00.05/ Захарченко Екатерина Сергеевна. - Саратов, 2014. - 23 с.
4. Матушанский, Г.У., Завада, Г.В., Романова, Л.М. Непрерывная профессиональная подготовка преподавателя высшей школы (на траектории ассистент – старший преподаватель – доцент): монография / Г.У. Матушанский, Г.В. Завада, Л.М. Романова. – Казань, 2011. – 152 с.
5. Sharafiddinov O.. Domlalar. – Тошкент: Ma'naviyat, 2009. – 280 б.
6. Шермухамедова Н. Фалсафа. – Тошкент: Idris Abdurauf Nashr, 2021. – 663 б.
7. Юсупов Э. Инсон камолотининг маънавий асослари. – Тошкент: Университет, 1998. – 184 б.